

Special Relativity, Lagrangian Theory and Quantum Mechanics

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Classical mechanics of a free particle is based on Newtonian mechanics and Lagrangian/Hamilton theories. A single frame of reference is chosen (the lab) and particles with the same mass m_0 (for example) moving at different velocities are considered in the free particle scenario (i.e. in the absence of force (potentials)).

We argue that the above is identical to considering a single particle with mass m_0 at time $t=0$ and $x=0$ viewed by various frames moving at different constant velocities $-v$. From the point of view of each frame, the particle moves at a velocity v . Thus the Newtonian picture of an m_0 particle moving at different speeds may be considered as a problem of special relativity. We argue (as in (1)) that $(x,t)=(0,t)$ transforms to (x',t') such that $x'/t'=v$. If one uses a metric $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$ (first row) $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$ second row, one may derive special relativistic relationships. In particular, one may obtain the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ if (p,E) and (x,t) transform in the same manner. We argue that the relationships obtained from special relativity pertain to classical mechanics and so one may mathematically obtain a function $L(v)$ such that $p=dL/dv$ and $E=pv - L$ for a free particle. In other words, special relativity governs Lagrangian results in the free particle case and is not really needed (in this special case). More importantly, it is special relativity which links E with t and p with x . As noted above, if one considers Newtonian mechanics in a single frame, the notion of special relativity does not arise, but the scaling of time by E and of x by p does i.e. $A = -Et+px$ is the classical action both relativistically and nonrelativistically. It is just not written in this way usually (i.e. $A = -m_0 \int \sqrt{1-v^2} dt$ ($c=1$) relativistically and $A = \int \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 dt$ nonrelativistically)

We argued in (2) that scaling must manifest itself physically and that it accounts for the physical wavelength in quantum mechanics. We argue that the quantum mechanics of a free particle ultimately follows from special relativity. As a result, ideas of quantum mechanics would not have appeared in Newtonian mechanics nor Lagrangian or Hamiltonian theories. When special relativity was developed it focused on transformations related to different frames, but these are equivalent to describing one frame with many different velocities (same m_0). Thus the physics in one frame is governed by special relativity even if it is nonrelativistic. We argue that the notion of the wavelength which appears even in the Schrodinger formalism follows from scaling of x by p which ultimately originates from special relativity. In other words, both the Lagrangian formalism and quantum mechanics follow from special relativity in the free particle case. We argue that free particle quantum mechanics is the starting point of overall quantum mechanics.

Special Relativity

As in (1), consider a particle with rest mass m_0 , momentum 0 at time $t=0$ and $x=0$. As seen from an arbitrary frame of reference this particle has Energy $=E(v,m_0)$, momentum $p(v,m_0)$ and a new x' and t' such that $x'/t' = v$. Consider a transformation:

$|a \ b|$

$|1 \ 0|$

$|b|$ which is unitary using the metric $|0 \ -1|$

In other words: $aa - bb = 1$ and $ab-ba = 0$. Applying this to: $(x,t) = (0,t_0)$ yields:

$X' = bt_0$ and $t' = at_0$ with $x'/t' = v$ so $b=va$. Then $aa-bb = 1 = aa(1-vv)$ or $a=1/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $B = v/\sqrt{1-vv}$. Applying this to $(p,E) = (0, m_0)$ yields: $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$. This automatically yields the form $p=Ev$ which becomes $p=mv$ nonrelativistically. This approach has already been shown in (1).

Consider the invariant: $A = -Et+px$ formed as an inner product of two 4-vectors using the metric shown above. As an invariant A does not depend on v , but E', p', x' , and t' do. Consider in particular

$$-E \frac{d}{dv} t' + p \frac{d}{dv} x' = -E \frac{d}{dv} (t_0/\sqrt{1-vv}) + p \frac{d}{dv} (v t_0 / \sqrt{1-vv}) = 0$$

$$\text{Thus: } dA/dv = 0 = -t \frac{dE}{dv} + x \frac{dp}{dv} \text{ and } x/t = dE./dv / dp/dv = v$$

Thus it is critical to have E associated with t and p with x for purely special relativistic considerations. Such a linking does not appear naturally in Newtonian mechanics or Lagrange/Hamiltonian theory. We emphasize this because we argue that the scaling of time by E and space (x) by p should be manifested physically. In other words, special relativity (without any notion of a Lagrangian or classical action at least for a free particle) suggests a physical wavelength exists proportional to $1/p$ and a physical frequency proportional to $1/E$. In other words quantum mechanics exists already at the level of free particle which is not linked to force or potential

Special Relativity and a Single Frame

It seems like the point of special relativity is to consider values of four vectors in different frames moving with different constant velocities v . This formalism, however, should apply to a single frame with many different particles with the same rest mass m_0 and different velocities. Thus theories such as Newtonian mechanics, Lagrangian/ Hamiltonian theory and nonrelativistic (and relativistic) quantum mechanics for a free particle should follow directly from special relativity applied to a single frame. A free particle is not linked to force or a potential so Lagrangian or Hamiltonian ideas should be purely mathematical mappings at this level.

In particular, one may suggest that $p = dL(v)/dv$. A solution is immediately: $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$. Mathematically this satisfies: $H = E = pv - L$. In other words the full free particle information is given by special relativity and the Lagrangian formalism yields no new information. It is interesting to note, however, that:

$$A = \text{classical action} = -Et + px \text{ ((1)) (both relativistically and nonrelativistically)}$$

For special relativity, $v=x/t$ as one considers $(0,m_0)$ ($x=0,t_0$) becoming a particle with velocity v as seen from different constant moving frames with velocity $-v$. In a single frame, however, one

has many particles moving with different velocities. x/t is still v in A , but a key point is that E scales t and p scales x . This suggests an independence namely a frequency proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength proportional to $1/p$. Thus space is mapped out strictly by p and time by E . This should be manifested physically.

Speculation on E Scaling t and p Scaling x

In the above section we considered special relativity i.e. a separate frame describing each velocity for a particle of rest mass m_0 and noted that $v=x/t$. We also noted that E scales t and p scales x in the invariant $-Et+px$. Thus $t=1/E$ and $x=1/p$ puts all particles with different velocities and the same m_0 on the same footing. $x/t = v$, but $E/p = 1/v$ so the special t and x are not linked to velocity motion. In fact, x linked to $1/p$ ignores E, t and t linked to $1/E$ ignores p, x . Why should there be a special footing if one has the same m_0 and different v in one frame? We argue that all of these different v , for the same m_0 are obtainable from Lorentz transforms of a single state $(p, E) = (0, m_0)$ and $(x, t) = (0, t_0)$. As a result, there is an equal footing in a sense for each. The invariant $-Et+px = m_0 t_0$ is linked directly to m_0 (energy) and time without x and p even appearing. Thus there is a kind of independence for E, t and p, x which has nothing to do with velocity. Allowing t proportional to $1/E$ and independently x proportional to $1/p$ seems to allow for this independence while maintaining an equal footing among particles with the same m_0 and different v (showing that they are Lorentz transformations of the same original state). (This is almost like rotating a vector, but here v is the parameter.) This is why we argue that scaling from special relativity is important and should be manifested physically.

Quantum Mechanics of a Free Particle Directly from Special Relativity

As a result, we suggest linking free particle quantum mechanics directly to physical scaling due to special relativity without any link to classical mechanical formalism. How can this be done using $A = -Et + px$? We suggest that scaling in time and space should be considered separately even though the particle moves with a velocity $v=x/t$ which is used to define E and p in the first place. It is possible to create an eigenvalue equation from A such that:

$$-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad ((2b))$$

Thus one may have a free particle moving at velocity $v=x/t$. It will have a momentum p (e.g. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc) which creates a physical spatial manifestation of the form $\exp(ipx)$ and independently a frequency from $\exp(-iEt)$. In general, one does not follow a particle in time as it interacts so $\exp(ipx)$ governs interactions which are based on p i.e. impulse. The particle may be moving fast or slow (with the same momentum) indicating that an interaction with a potential may occur quickly or slowly, but it is the impulse which is the same and seems to govern quantum interactions of a free particle. Given that a wavefunction may be decomposed into a linear superposition of free particle forms i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, the free particle seems to be important. For different energy levels, $\exp(-iEn t)$ comes into play allowing for interference at different times and changes in density with time. For a bound state with a single

energy E_n , the form $\exp(-iE_n t)$ does not play much of a role except for being linked to E_n . In the pure bound state, only spatial considerations are important in an interaction of the form $V(x)$ and so $\exp(ipx)$ is of main focus.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though Newtonian mechanics and Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theories were developed historically before special relativity, one may understand a free particle based solely on special relativity. In fact, one may derive the form of special relativity using a particle of rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ and insist on x,t transforming to x',t' with $v=x'/t'$ as viewed from a frame moving with velocity $-v$. Thus all velocities (for the same m_0) in a single frame are linked to many different constant moving frames governed by the special relativistic transformation which holds for (x,t) and (p,E) . A special metric is needed so $xx-tt = \text{constant}$. $-Et+px$ is an invariant suggesting that E scales time and p space as a purely special relativistic phenomenon. We argue that the quantum mechanics of a free particle, which is the basis of more general quantum mechanics is the physical manifestation of the scaling using the differential equations: $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ and $i\hbar d/dt \exp(-iE t) = E \exp(-iE t)$. In other words special relativity and free particle quantum mechanics are inseparable.

References

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